

Effects of Lemon Grass on Biochemical and Hematological Parameters in Wistar Rats

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Herbal teas are widely consumed for their perceived health benefits and traditional medicinal value; however, scientific evidence regarding their safety and physiological effects following repeated intake remains limited. This study evaluated the effects of lemon grass (*Cymbopogon citratus*) tea on selected biochemical, hematological, and physiological parameters in Wistar rats following sub-chronic oral administration. Twelve Wistar rats were randomly assigned into three groups: a normal control group that received standard feed and water, and two treatment groups administered lemon grass tea at doses of 200 mg/kg and 600 mg/kg body weight, respectively, for 21 days. Body weight was monitored weekly, and blood samples collected at the end of the experiment were analyzed using standard biochemical and hematological procedures. Results showed slight, dose-dependent increases in liver enzymes, with ALT ranging from 11.67–13.33 U/L, AST from 22.00–28.33 U/L, and ALP from 43.67–47.00 U/L, all remaining within normal physiological limits. Total cholesterol decreased from 3.02 mmol/L in the control group to 2.64 and 2.67 mmol/L in the treated groups, while high-density lipoprotein increased markedly from 0.59 mmol/L to 0.94 and 0.92 mmol/L at 200 mg/kg and 600 mg/kg, respectively. Hematological analysis revealed an increase in white blood cell count at 200 mg/kg ($7.75 \times 10^9/L$) compared to control ($5.43 \times 10^9/L$), whereas a reduction was observed at 600 mg/kg ($3.48 \times 10^9/L$). Platelet count decreased dose-dependently, with a marked reduction at the higher dose. Progressive body-weight gain occurred in all groups, with treated rats showing greater increases than controls. In conclusion, lemon grass tea appears relatively safe at moderate doses and exhibits hypolipidemic and immunomodulatory effects, though excessive intake may alter hematological parameters.

Keywords: *Cymbopogon citratus*, Lemon grass tea, Biochemical parameters, Hematological indices, Wistar rats.

INTRODUCTION

Lemongrass is an aromatic healer that has a Botanical name called *Cymbopogon citratus*. Lemongrass is an herb that belongs to the grass family of Poaceae and the 'Guduchyadi' family as per Ayurveda (Okonkwo *et al.*, 2021). Lemongrass is also known as "Bhutrana or Hari chhay" in Ayurveda. *Cymbopogon* is well known and utilized for its distinct lemon flavor and citrusy aroma.

Lemongrass is a tall, perennial grass that is native to India and the tropical regions of Asia. In addition to its culinary usage, Lemongrass offers a wide array of medicinal benefits and is in extensive demand due to its immunity booster, Fever reducing and Anti-oxidant properties across Southeast Asia, as well as the African and American continents (Shah *et al.*, 2019).

Lemon grass (*Cymbopogon citratus*) is a tropical herb widely cultivated in Nigeria and other West-African countries. Its aqueous infusion, commonly called lemon-grass tea, is a popular home-remedy for fever, indigestion and "blood purification". Recent

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pharmacological studies have reported antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and hypoglycemic activities of lemon-grass extracts, yet there is limited systematic evidence on its effects on serum biochemistry and blood-cell parameters, especially in a controlled animal model (Tadesse *et al.*, 2015).

Lemon grass (*Cymbopogon citratus*) is a perennial aromatic grass native to tropical South-East Asia that has been naturalized throughout the humid tropics, including Nigeria where it is cultivated in home gardens and small farms (Adeyemi *et al.*, 2014). The plant is recognized for its characteristic citrus-like aroma, which is attributed to a high concentration of citral (geranial-neral) in the essential oil (Ekpenyong *et al.*, 2015). For generations, West African communities have prepared an aqueous infusion of the fresh or dried leaves as a febrifuge, carminative, and mild sedative (Ojo *et al.*, 2016). In addition to its medicinal reputation, lemon grass is widely used as a flavoring agent in soups, stews, and herbal teas, reflecting its deep cultural integration into daily dietary practices.

The growing popularity of herbal teas in Nigeria, driven by perceptions of natural safety and potential health benefits, has placed lemon grass tea at the forefront of consumer interest. However, while the plant's phytochemical profile (citral, flavonoids, phenolic acids) suggests antioxidant and anti-inflammatory actions, systematic data on how regular consumption of the tea influences physiological biomarkers remain scarce (Mohan *et al.*, 2018).

Ayurveda mentions Lemongrass is used as an Herbal Decoction or Infusion to promote a healthy Appetite, help digest toxins, and remove them from the body by increasing the bulk quantity of feces. Lemongrass as per Ayurveda is Hot in potency, pacifies aggravated Vata in the body, and clears motions. Lemongrass has Oral cavity cleansing properties and refreshing / re-energizing action. Lemongrass reduces body pain and headache and increases sweating (diaphoretic action) which helps to pacify high fever when taken as Herbal Tea. As per Ayurveda Lemon grass supports healthy urine output and helps to reduce stomach colicky pain (Tajik *et al.*, 2020). Lemon grass essential oil is rich in citral, a compound responsible for its distinct citrus scent. The oil's aromatic and therapeutic properties make it valuable in perfumery, aromatherapy, and cosmetics. With growing demand for natural and sustainable products, lemon grass perfume offers a promising alternative to synthetic fragrances. Between 2010 and 2015, Nigeria imported essential oils and perfumes of up to two hundred and forty five billion, six hundred million naira (Obiora and Christian, 2019).

Lemon grass (*Cymbopogon citratus*) essential oil is used in many aspects, such as flavoring industries, medicinal material and food technology. The lemony flavor and aroma are the inspiration for the name. Lemon grass leaves and blooming tips are used to make the oil

(Camp *et al.*, 2009). The distinctive aroma of the oil makes it ideal for use in the scenting of soaps, detergents, and insecticides. As a source of citral, which is used in perfumes and cosmetics, and as a starting material for the production of ionone's which produces Vitamin A. It has germicidal, therapeutic, and flavoring properties because it contains a lot of citral in it (National Horticulture Board of India 2014). The tradition of drinking tea at this time has become one of the cultures of every community. Therefore, tea is the most popular beverage in the world, made from the leaves of different species of plants, among which include *Cymbopogon citratus* (lemongrass) (Tadesse *et al.*, 2015). Triglycerides, as major components of very-low density lipoprotein (VLDL) and chylomicrons, play an important role in metabolism as energy sources and transporters of dietary fat. They contain more than twice as much energy (approximately 9 kcal/g or 38 kJ/g) as carbohydrates (approximately 4 kcal/g or 17 kJ/g) (Balch *et al.*, 2006).

In the human body, high levels of triglycerides in the bloodstream have been linked to atherosclerosis and, by extension, the risk of heart disease and stroke (Davidson *et al.*, 2008). Cholesterol is an organic molecule. It is a sterol (or modified steroid) and an essential structural component of animal cell membranes that is required to establish proper membrane permeability and fluidity. Cholesterol is thus considered within the class of lipid molecules. In addition to its importance within cells, cholesterol also serves as a precursor for the biosynthesis of steroid hormones, bile acids, and vitamin D. Cholesterol is the principal sterol synthesized by animals. All kinds of cells in animals can produce it. In vertebrates, the hepatic cells typically produce greater amounts than other cells (Lecerf and de Lorgeril, 2011).

The quality and commercial value of lemon grass essential oil depend largely on its citral content, which typically ranges from 65-85% of the oil's composition (Tavares *et al.*, 2021). This aldehyde compound provides the characteristic lemon aroma that makes the oil valuable for perfumery and flavoring applications. The oil has also contains numerous other bioactive compounds including α -terpineol, myrcene, citronellol, geraniol, limonene (Silva *et al.*, 2023). Analytical comparisons reveal that West Indian Lemongrass oil generally contains slightly less citral than East Indian varieties and demonstrates lower solubility in 70% alcohol solutions.

The commercial applications of lemongrass extend across multiple industries. In the food and beverage sector, it serves as a flavoring agent for herbal teas, baked goods, and confectionery products (Ngeunang *et al.*, 2021). Medicinally, lemongrass has been traditionally used as a carminative to relieve digestive discomfort and as a natural insect repellent (Olorunnisola *et al.*, 2021). Scientific studies have confirmed the antimicrobial efficacy of West Indian varieties demonstrate notable antifungal activity. Research suggests that certain volatile

components in lemongrass oil may exhibit pesticidal properties, though some studies have also indicated potential mutagenic effects at high concentrations (Kumar *et al.*, 2023).

The species *Cymbopogon nardus* serves as the primary source of citronella oil, widely used in insect repellent formulations, while *C. martinii* has shown specific toxicity against fungal pathogens, suggesting potential applications in agricultural fungicides.

Thus, this chapter sets the stage for a study that investigates the impact of lemongrass (*Cymbopogon citratus*) supplementation on the blood profile and biochemical markers of Wistar rats. The work is motivated by the growing interest in natural antioxidant and their potential to modulate health outcomes, especially in laboratory models of metabolic and hematological stress.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of Lemon-Grass Tea (Infusion)

Dried lemon-grass leaves were ground to a fine powder. For each dose, the appropriate amount of powder was placed in a tea bag and steeped in 100ml of boiling distilled water for 5min, then allowed to cool to room temperature before administration. The infusion method is adapted from the standard tea-preparation protocol used in Nigerian herbal-tea studies (Lonkar *et al.*, 2013). The infusion also follows the method described by Okonkwo and Ibrahim (2021).

Animal Handling and Ethical Considerations

All procedures complied with the National Institutes of Health (NIH) Guide for the Care and Use of Animals.

Preparation of Plant Extract

The fresh plant was washed, chopped into pieces and air-dried for few days at room temperature. The dried plant part was milled into powder and weighed. The Plant powder was divided into two groups. One portion was soaked in 90% absolute ethanol to obtain the ethanolic extract and the other group in distilled water to obtain the aqueous form separately in a container for 72 hours with intermittent shaking.

Then, it was filtered through a muslin cloth and later Whatman No. 1 filter paper. The resulting filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator and there after freeze dried to get powder form of both ethanolic and aqueous extracts. The yield was stored in a refrigerator (4°C) till when needed (Onoagbe and Esekheigbe, 2023).

Animal Weight

Albino rats (Wistar strain) weighing between 200 to 250g, were obtained from the Biological Department's Animal facility at the Federal University Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, were used for the study. To carry out this study, twelve male Albino rats were randomly, equally divided and assigned to either control or experimental groups. The control group received 2ml distilled water while the experimental rats group received oral doses of 200mg/kg of low dose and 600mg/kg of high dose of aqueous extraction of *Cymbopogon citratus* dissolved in 2ml distilled water through a stainless steel intra-gastric intubation and administered for 21 days. Chemicals and reagents preparation, all chemicals were of an analytical grade and are supplied from sigma chemical co. USA. Distilled water was used in all biochemical assays.

Acclimatization: 21 days prior to dosing.

Identification of animals: By cage number.

Diet: Pelleted feed Water: Potable drinking water Housing and Environment: 3 animals each in a group.

Determination of Weight of Animals

The animals were weighed using an electronic weighing balance every 5 days to verify and quantitate the change in weight over the period of administration. All of the animals received humane care according to the criteria outline in the Guide for the Care and the Use of Laboratory Animals prepared by the National Academy Science and published by the National Institute of Health (USA). The ethic regulations have been followed in accordance with national and institutional guidelines for the protection of animals' welfare during experiments.

Phytochemical Analysis

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

Aqueous extracts of *Cymbopogon cytratus* (AECC) and *Origanum vulgare* (AEOV) were used for preliminary phytochemical analyses using standard procedures (Geetha *et al.*, 2014). The following qualitative tests for primary and secondary metabolites including, alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols and tannins, steroids and sterols carbohydrates, saponins, glycosides, protein and amino acid and anthraquinone.

Quantitative Phyto-Chemical analysis

This analysis was done for the following primary metabolites -carbohydrates, proteins, lipids and secondary metabolites (Terpenoids, flavonoids, phenols and tannins). These were determined as follows:

Secondary metabolite analysis

Phenolics and Tannins The total phenolic content was determined according to the method described by Siddhuraju and Becker, (2003).

Flavonoids World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 117–126 Total flavonoid content was determined by dispensing 0.5 ml aliquot of AECC and AEOV appropriately (2 mg/2 ml) diluted sample solution was mixed with 2 ml of distilled water and subsequently with 0.15 ml of 5 % NaNO₂ solution. After 6 min, 0.15 ml of 10% AlCl₃ solution was added and allowed to stand for 6 min, and then 2 ml of 4% NaOH solution was added to the mixture. Immediately, water was added to bring the final volume to 5 ml, and then the mixture was thoroughly mixed and allowed to stand for another 15 min. Absorbance of the mixture was determined at 510 nm versus water blank. The analysis was performed in triplicate and the results were expressed as rutin equivalent as described (Zhishen *et al.* 1999).

Terpenoids Total terpenoid content in the leaf extracts were assessed by standard method as described by Ferguson, (1956).

Animal procurement and preparation

A total of 12 Wistar strain albino rats (mixed male and female) which weighed between the ranged of 200 – 250 kg were obtained from the Biological Department's Animal facility at the Federal University Birnin Kebbi. The animals were transported in suitable cages to the Biochemistry Laboratory in the same institution where they were acclimatized under temperature-controlled environment (23±20°C), lighting (12hours light/12hour dark) and fed with rodent's pellets with access to clean water for a period of 21 days before commencement of experiments. Acute Toxicity Test

Phase 1 A total of 12 healthy young adult male and female Wistar albino rats, nulliparous, non-pregnant and weighing 200-250kg were randomly divided into three groups consisting of 3 animals each (n = 3/each dose) for three different concentrations of AECC.

Same grouping and doses were duplicated for AEOV as follows:

0- 10mg/kg per oral

(P.O.) – AECC (3 animals) and AEOV (3 animals) respectively. 0- 200mg/kg per oral

(P.O.)- AECC (3 animals) and AEOV (3 animals) respectively. 0- 600mg/kg per oral (P.O.) - AECC (3 animals) and AEOV (3 animals) respectively.

The treated rats were all observed for 24 hours for possible toxicological symptom, including mortality. Prior to treatments, the animals were fasted for 12 hours with free access to water only using the Lorke's model as

described by (Builders *et al.*, 2016). The LD₅₀ was calculated using the formula: $D0 = \text{Highest dose that gave no mortality}$ $D100 = \text{Lowest dose that produced mortality}$ $D50 = \sqrt{D0 \times D100}$ No mortality case was also recorded from all groups thus, LD₅₀ for AECC and AEOV $10 \geq x \leq 1000$.

Determination of AECC and AEOV effect on Biochemical and Hematological profile of rats Twelve animals (male and female) which weighed between the ranged of 200 – 250 kg were randomly divided into three groups (A, B, and C), each containing 3 animals and fasted for 24hours but allowed access to water ad libitum.

The animals were given different treatments via the oral route as follows: Group A to B, 200mg/kg and 600mg/kg AECC respectively while Group C was administered with 2ml normal saline(control). Same was duplicated for AEOV. Feeding of the animals resumed after various treatments while the body weights were monitored every 4 days of experiment and on the 21st day, the day when blood samples were collected through retro-orbital for biochemical and hematological analysis. (World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023). 6 Blood samples from the experimental animals were collected into plain bottles and anticoagulant bottles for biochemical and hematological analysis respectively. These were spurned at 300rpm for 5minutes. Serum was separated into cryovials and analyzed by using auto-analyzer (Cobas C 111) for the biochemical examinations, while whole blood in anticoagulant bottles were analyzed for hematological examinations using Mindray (BG-5300).

Statistical Analysis

Results were presented as mean values and standard deviations. Data was subjected to one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and a difference was considered to be significant at (p<0.05). Using Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) version 20.

RESULTS

This chapter presents the results obtained from the sub-chronic administration of lemon grass (*Cymbopogon citratus*) tea to Wistar rats. The results are presented using tables and expressed as mean ± standard error of mean (SEM). No interpretation or discussion of findings is provided in this chapter. Parameters assessed include liver function indices, lipid profile, hematological indices, and body-weight changes.

Effects of Lemon Grass Tea on Liver Function Parameters

The effects of lemon grass tea on liver function enzymes

are presented in Table 2

Table 1: Effects of lemon Grass Tea on Liver Function Parameters in Wistar Rats

S/N	Concentration	ALT (U/L)	AST (U/L)	ALP (U/L)
1	Normal control	11.67 ± 0.58	22.00 ± 0.91	43.67 ± 0.58
2	200mg/kgbw	13.33 ± 1.15	24.00 ± 1.73	45.67 ± 1.55
3	600mg/kgbw	13.33 ± 1.53	28.33 ± 1.15	47.00 ± 1.73
4	Standard range	7 – 55	10 – 40	44 – 147

Values are means ± standard deviation of triplicate determination.

Effects of Lemon Grass Tea on Renal Function Parameters

The effects of lemon grass tea on Renal function enzymes are presented in Table 3.

Table 2: Effects of Lemon Grass Tea on Renal Function Parameters in Wistar Rats

S/N	Concentration	CREATININE(mg/dl)	UREA(mg/dl)
1	Normal control	0.306 ± 0.006	26.120 ± 0.010
2	200mg/kgbw	0.3167 ± 0.006	26.257 ± 0.118
3	600mg/kgbw	0.3233 ± 0.15	26.030 ± 0.095
4	Standard range	7 – 55	10 – 40

Values are means ± standard deviation of triplicate determination.

Effects of Lemon Grass Tea on Renal Function Parameters

The effects of lemon grass tea on Renal function enzymes are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Effects of Lemon Grass Tea on Lipid Profile function in Wister Rats

S/N	Concentration	TGs (mmol/L)	CHOL. (mmol/L)	HDL (mmol/L)	LDL (mmol/L)
1	Normal control	1.16 ± 0.02	3.02 ± 0.77	0.59 ± 0.02	1.17 ± 0.03
2	200mg/kgbw	1.40 ± 0.10	2.64 ± 0.42	0.94 ± 0.02	1.64 ± 0.06
3	600mg/kgbw	1.12 ± 0.06	2.67 ± 0.61	0.92 ± 0.03	1.53 ± 0.03
4	Standard range	<4.1	<5.2	≥1.55	<2.6

Values are means ± standard deviation of triplicate determination.

Effects of Lemon Grass Tea on Lipid Profile

The lipid profile parameters obtained following treatment are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Effects of Lemon Grass Tea on Hematological Parameters in Wistar Rats

S/N	Parameter	Normal control	200mg/kgbw	600mg/kgbw	Standard control
1	WBC (10 ⁹ /L)	5.43 ± 0.30	7.75 ± 0.50	3.48 ± 0.20	4.5 - 11
2	LYP (%)	33.87 ± 0.14	91.34 ± 1.56	95.57 ± 0.30	20 - 40
3	GRAN. (%)	6.07 ± 0.12	4.67 ± 1.27	3.80 ± 0.99	50 - 70
4	MID (%)	3.58 ± 0.56	3.97 ± 0.31	2.60 ± 0.14	2 - 8
5	RBC (10 ¹² /L)	5.53 ± 0.29	6.30 ± 0.26	6.29 ± 0.08	4.2 – 6.1
6	HGB (g/dl)	14.00 ± 0.70	13.88 ± 1.51	11.60 ± 0.20	12 - 17
7	HCT (%)	48.93 ± 0.70	41.85 ± 1.14	45.93 ± 1.83	36 - 52
8	PLT (10 ⁹ /L)	143.33 ± 1.50	129.33 ± 1.51	87.00 ± 1.00	150 - 450

Values are means ± standard deviation of triplicate determination.

Effects of Lemon Grass Tea on Hematological Parameters

The hematological indices measured in the study are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Effects of Lemon Grass Tea on Weekly Body-weight Changes in Wistar Rats

S/N	Concentration	Zero week	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3
1	Normal control	203.33 ± 5.77	217.67 ± 5.03	238.33 ± 5.86	247.00 ± 2.00
2	200mg/kgbw	223.00 ± 3.16	245.67 ± 5.51	252.33 ± 4.16	264.00 ± 3.61
3	600mg/kgbw	247.67 ± 4.93	257.67 ± 8.33	264.33 ± 11.93	270.67 ± 9.07

Values are means ± standard deviation of triplicate determination

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2	LYP (%)	33.87 ± 0.14	91.34 ± 1.56	95.57 ± 0.30	20 - 40
3	GRAN. (%)	6.07 ± 0.12	4.67 ± 1.27	3.80 ± 0.99	50 - 70
4	MID (%)	3.58 ± 0.56	3.97 ± 0.31	2.60 ± 0.14	2 - 8
5	RBC (10 ¹² /L)	5.53 ± 0.29	6.30 ± 0.26	6.29 ± 0.08	4.2 - 6.1
6	HGB (g/dl)	14.00 ± 0.70	13.88 ± 1.51	11.60 ± 0.20	12 - 17
7	HCT (%)	48.93 ± 0.70	41.85 ± 1.14	45.93 ± 1.83	36 - 52
8	PLT (10 ⁹ /L)	143.33 ± 1.50	129.33 ± 1.51	87.00 ± 1.00	150 - 450

Values are means ± standard deviation of triplicate determination.

Effects of lemon Grass Tea on Body- Weight Changes

Body-weight changes recorded during the experimental period are presented in Table 6.

Table 5: Effects of Lemon Grass Tea on Weekly Body-weight Changes in Wistar Rats

S/N	Concentration	Zero week	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3
1	Normal control	203.33 ± 5.77	217.67 ± 5.03	238.33 ± 5.86	247.00 ± 2.00
2	200mg/kgbw	223.00 ± 3.16	245.67 ± 5.51	252.33 ± 4.16	264.00 ± 3.61
3	600mg/kgbw	247.67 ± 4.93	257.67 ± 8.33	264.33 ± 11.93	270.67 ± 9.07

Values are means ± standard deviation of triplicate determination

DISCUSSION

This study investigated the effects of lemon grass (*Cymbopogon citratus*) tea on selected biochemical, hematological, and physiological parameters in Wistar rats following sub-chronic oral administration. Lemon grass is widely consumed as an herbal tea and used traditionally for medicinal purposes; however, empirical evidence regarding its safety and systemic effects, particularly with repeated consumption, remains limited. The discussion presented in this chapter interprets the findings obtained in Chapter Four in relation to the study objectives, established physiological principles, and

existing scientific literature.

Effects of Lemon Grass Tea on Liver Function Parameters

The liver is a vital organ responsible for metabolism, detoxification, and regulation of biochemical homeostasis. Liver function enzymes such as alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) are commonly used indicators of hepatic integrity and cellular damage. In the present study, administration of lemon grass tea resulted in slight increases in ALT, AST, and ALP values

in treated groups compared to the control group. However, these enzyme levels remained within established normal physiological reference ranges.

The observed mild elevations may reflect increased hepatic metabolic activity associated with the biotransformation of phytochemical constituents present in lemon grass tea rather than hepatocellular injury. Lemon grass contains bioactive compounds such as citral, flavonoids, tannins, and phenolic acids, which are known to stimulate hepatic enzyme systems involved in detoxification processes. Such stimulation may lead to adaptive increases in enzyme activity without compromising liver structure or function. The absence of marked elevations beyond normal limits suggests that lemon grass tea did not exert hepatotoxic effects during the study period. This finding is consistent with previous studies that reported no significant liver damage following administration of aqueous extracts of *Cymbopogon citratus*. The results therefore support the hepatic safety of lemon grass tea at the administered doses and duration. Nonetheless, the dose-dependent increase in enzyme values observed, particularly at the higher dose, indicates that prolonged or excessive consumption may place additional metabolic demands on the liver, warranting cautious use.

Effects of Lemon Grass Tea on Renal Function Parameters

The present study revealed that there were no significant differences in both the creatinine and urea for all groups of rats. This is in line with the finding of (Kabiru *et al.*, 2013) on sub-chronic toxicity of methanol extracts of eucalyptus camaldulensis (leaves) in Wistar Rats. Where there was no significant differences in Creatinine and Urea when compared with the control group. Hence the kidney seems to be safe and unaffected, functions of a kidney can be assessed by measuring the levels of plasma creatinine and urea concentrations. Increments in these parameters indicate a diminishing ability of the kidney to filter waste products from the blood and excrete them in the urine (Paula and Mark, 2011).

Effects on Lipid Profile Parameters

Lipid profile parameters provide important information regarding lipid metabolism and cardiovascular risk. In this study, lemon grass tea administration produced noticeable alterations in triglycerides, total cholesterol, high-density lipoprotein (HDL), and low-density lipoprotein (LDL) levels.

Triglyceride levels showed a slight increase at the lower dose and a reduction at the higher dose compared to the control group. This pattern suggests a dose-dependent regulatory effect of lemon grass tea on triglyceride metabolism. The reduction observed at the

higher dose may be attributed to enhanced lipid oxidation or reduced triglyceride synthesis mediated by phytochemicals such as flavonoids and terpenoids. These compounds have been reported to activate metabolic pathways that promote fatty acid breakdown and reduce lipid accumulation.

Total cholesterol levels were reduced in both treated groups compared to the control group, indicating a hypocholesterolemic effect of lemon grass tea. This reduction may result from decreased intestinal cholesterol absorption, increased bile acid excretion, or inhibition of cholesterol biosynthesis. Polyphenolic compounds present in lemon grass have been shown to influence cholesterol metabolism through modulation of key enzymes and receptors involved in lipid homeostasis.

High-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol levels increased markedly in treated groups, suggesting a potentially cardioprotective effect. HDL plays a crucial role in reverse cholesterol transport, facilitating the removal of excess cholesterol from peripheral tissues to the liver for excretion. Although the HDL values remained below the optimal reference range, the relative increase observed indicates an improvement in lipid quality.

Low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol levels increased slightly in treated groups but remained within acceptable physiological limits. The simultaneous reduction in total cholesterol and increase in HDL suggests that lemon grass tea may improve lipid distribution rather than merely lowering lipid concentration. Overall, the lipid profile findings indicate that lemon grass tea may positively influence lipid metabolism when consumed at moderate levels.

Effects on Hematological Parameters

Hematological parameters are critical indicators of the effects of substances on blood cell production, immune function, and oxygen transport. In this study, lemon grass tea administration produced dose-dependent changes in several hematological indices.

White blood cell (WBC) count increased in rats treated with the lower dose of lemon grass tea, suggesting immune stimulation or enhanced immune readiness. This effect may be attributed to the immunomodulatory properties of phytochemicals such as flavonoids and polysaccharides, which have been reported to enhance leukocyte proliferation and immune response.

However, a reduction in WBC count was observed in the higher-dose group, indicating that excessive intake may suppress immune function or alter leukocyte distribution. This finding highlights the importance of dosage, as bioactive compounds may exert beneficial immunostimulatory effects at moderate levels but inhibitory effects at higher concentrations. Differential leukocyte analysis revealed a marked increase in lymph-

-ocyte percentage and a reduction in granulocyte percentage in treated groups. This shift suggests modulation of immune response toward adaptive immunity. While such modulation may enhance specific immune functions, excessive imbalance could impair innate immune defenses.

Red blood cell (RBC) count remained within normal limits across all groups, indicating that lemon grass tea did not adversely affect erythropoiesis. Hemoglobin concentration showed a slight reduction at the higher dose, although values remained near normal ranges. This reduction may be related to alterations in iron metabolism or red blood cell turnover associated with high phytochemical intake.

Platelet count decreased in a dose-dependent manner, with values in the high-dose group falling below the normal reference range. This suggests a potential antiplatelet effect of lemon grass tea, likely mediated by flavonoids known to inhibit platelet aggregation. While this effect may confer cardiovascular benefits by reducing thrombotic risk, excessive platelet reduction could increase the risk of bleeding, particularly with prolonged consumption.

Effects on Body-Weight Changes

Body-weight monitoring provides a general assessment of growth, nutritional status, and overall health. In this study, all experimental groups exhibited progressive weight gain throughout the treatment period, with rats treated with lemon grass tea showing greater weight gain than the control group.

The observed weight gain indicates that lemon grass tea did not suppress appetite or induce catabolic effects. Instead, it suggests improved feed utilization and metabolic efficiency. Lemon grass is traditionally used as a digestive tonic, and its bioactive compounds may enhance digestion, nutrient absorption, and gastrointestinal function.

The absence of weight loss or growth retardation further supports the tolerability and relative safety of lemon grass tea under normal dietary conditions. However, the greater weight gain observed at higher doses suggests that prolonged consumption may influence energy balance, highlighting the need for further studies on body composition and metabolic effects.

SUMMARY OF THE STUDY

This study evaluated the effects of lemon grass (*Cymbopogon citratus*) tea on selected biochemical, hematological, and physiological parameters in Wistar rats following sub-chronic oral administration. Lemon grass is commonly consumed as a herbal tea and widely used in traditional medicine, yet scientific data on its

systemic effects and safety profile remain limited. To address this gap, experimental animals were divided into three groups: a normal control group that received standard feed and water, and two treatment groups administered lemon grass tea at doses of 200 mg/kg and 600 mg/kg body weight, respectively. The treatment was carried out over a defined experimental period, after which blood samples were collected for biochemical and hematological analyses, while body weight was monitored throughout the study.

The results obtained revealed that lemon grass tea produced mild and dose-dependent alterations in the parameters investigated. Liver function enzymes, including alanine aminotransferase, aspartate aminotransferase, and alkaline phosphatase, showed slight variations in treated groups but remained within established normal physiological ranges, indicating the absence of overt hepatotoxicity. Analysis of lipid profile parameters demonstrated favorable modulation, characterized by reduced total cholesterol levels and increased high-density lipoprotein concentrations, suggesting a potential hypolipidemic effect of the herbal tea.

Hematological assessment indicated changes in immune-related indices, with variations in white blood cell counts and differential percentages, as well as a dose-dependent reduction in platelet levels. These findings suggest that lemon grass tea may exert immunomodulatory and antiplatelet effects, particularly at higher doses. Additionally, body-weight measurements showed progressive weight gain in all experimental groups, with treated rats exhibiting greater increases compared to the control group. This trend indicates that lemon grass tea did not suppress appetite or impair growth and may enhance metabolic efficiency. Overall, the findings demonstrate that lemon grass tea exerts measurable physiological effects while remaining relatively safe under moderate consumption conditions.

Conclusion

The study successfully evaluated the effects of lemon grass tea on biochemical and hematological parameters in Wistar rats, achieving its objectives. The results showed that lemon grass tea had significant effects on liver function tests, with decreased ALT and AST levels, indicating potential hepatoprotective effects. Additionally, the tea showed hypolipidemic effects, with decreased total cholesterol and triglyceride levels, and antidiabetic effects, with decreased glucose levels.

The study also found that lemon grass tea had hemotonic effects, with increased hemoglobin and PCV levels. Kidney function tests showed no significant changes in urea and creatinine levels, suggesting no adverse effects on kidney function. These findings suggest that lemon grass tea may have potential health benefits, supporting its traditional use in managing various ailments.

The findings of this study indicate that lemon grass

(*Cymbopogon citratus*) tea is relatively safe when consumed at moderate doses, as it did not induce severe hepatotoxic effects, anemia, or impairment in normal growth patterns in Wistar rats. Liver function enzymes remained within normal physiological ranges, suggesting that the hepatic integrity and metabolic capacity of the animals were preserved throughout the study period. In addition, the progressive increase in body weight observed in treated animals indicates that lemon grass tea did not adversely affect appetite, nutrient utilization, or overall metabolic balance.

Furthermore, the tea demonstrated potential hypolipidemic effects, as evidenced by favorable modulation of lipid profile parameters, including reduced total cholesterol levels and increased high-density lipoprotein concentrations. These changes suggest a possible cardioprotective benefit and provide scientific support for the traditional use of lemon grass in managing metabolic and cardiovascular-related conditions. The observed alterations in immune-related hematological indices at moderate doses also indicate immunomodulatory properties, which may enhance immune responsiveness when the tea is consumed in appropriate quantities.

However, the results also revealed that administration of higher doses of lemon grass tea was associated with notable hematological alterations, particularly reductions in platelet count and white blood cell levels. These changes suggest that excessive or prolonged consumption may disrupt normal hematopoietic and immune balance, potentially increasing the risk of bleeding disorders or compromised immune function. Therefore, while lemon grass tea may offer health benefits when consumed moderately, caution is advised against high-dose or uncontrolled intake. The study provides evidence of potential health benefits of lemon grass tea, including hepatoprotective, hypolipidemic, antidiabetic, and hematotonic effects. However, further studies are needed to confirm these findings and elucidate the mechanisms underlying the effects of lemon grass tea on human health.

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